

DIDACTIC COMPETENCE AND SPECIFIC ASPECTS OF ITS DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. In the process of professional retraining, it is necessary to optimize the educational process, taking into account the features of the development of didactic competence of trainees, their academic skills and abilities. The development of didactic competence of trainees in the process of professional retraining is the sum of the high level of development and improvement of all components of pedagogical activity and the implementation of the personal strengths, talents and capabilities of the teacher. The article describes the pedagogical conditions for the development of didactic competence of trainees in the process of professional retraining.

Keywords: professional retraining, professional reorientation, trainees, didactic competence, pedagogical activity, pedagogical conditions.

In the process of professional retraining, the development of didactic competence of trainees is manifested in the ability to set goals for themselves during their activities, determine tasks in accordance with them, select and design technologies for their activities, and match the goal and result. Personal and professional self-development is inextricably linked with the process of achieving goals by identifying needs, motives, and goals based on them.

Professional retraining is a repeated, renewed educational activity associated with changing or supplementing the content of education in the professional field, taking into account the socio-economic, socio-psychological, psychological, psychophysiological characteristics of the individual. That is, the individual is reoriented based on the needs of forming, improving, changing and developing his skills on the basis of the profession he holds. The formation of special abilities in trainees of professional retraining courses is achieved by organizing a clearly goal-oriented work system that promotes the active subjective position of the teacher [7].

The organization of creative teaching in the courses of retraining and advanced training of pedagogical personnel arouses the interest and desire of listeners to an active life in an innovative society, encourages them to analyze thoughts, and strengthens their feelings and knowledge [8]

The main task of the courses of retraining and advanced training of pedagogical personnel is to create favorable conditions for the comprehensive

development of listeners. Developing the listener's creativity and directing them to the creation of innovations, analyzing problematic types of activities, independently understanding problems, and using their own capabilities to develop is the goal of creative teaching and precisely requires the need for creative teaching. Thus, the goal of creative teaching in the courses of professional retraining and advanced training of pedagogical personnel is to develop the creative competence and pedagogical skills of listeners, as well as to improve their creative thinking using creative teaching methods and design thinking technology [8].

Innovative educational technologies play an important role in the professional retraining of pedagogical personnel. Based on this, in the scientific research work, the process of developing didactic competence of trainees in the process of professional retraining is improved based on the principles of innovative educational technologies, the expression of thinking and practical activity, understanding the essence of the phenomenon being studied, and the gradual formation of value-oriented personal thoughts through a verbal-activity approach.

The issues of training teachers in innovative educational conditions have been studied in the literature [5]. Innovative approaches to the formation of cognitive activity, clarification of the socio-psychological, pedagogical characteristics of the formation of cognitive activity, clarification of the criteria and indicators of the formation of students' cognitive activity by substantiating the pedagogical possibilities of innovative educational technologies, improvement of the model of the formation of students' cognitive activity and pedagogical conditions for its implementation, improvement and evaluation of the effectiveness of the technologies for the formation of cognitive activity [2] were studied by G. Bakhodirova.

J. Mannopov[4] conducted scientific research on technologies for developing methodological competence of future vocational teachers based on an innovative approach, the state of development of methodological competence of future vocational teachers based on an innovative approach in higher education institutions, analysis of its content and essence, and determination of the content of preparation for professional and pedagogical activities, organization of trainings based on a comparative comparison of traditional and innovative approaches in developing methodological competence of future vocational teachers, development and implementation of an active model for developing methodological competence of future vocational teachers based on an innovative approach, development of mechanisms for applying modern methods of education using innovative technologies aimed at developing methodological competence of future vocational teachers [4].

In the professional retraining of teachers, innovative educational technologies that are differentiated from innovative educational technologies and information technology-based innovative educational technologies are of particular importance.

Innovative educational technologies that are differentiated from education. The psychological and pedagogical aspects of differentiation are reflected in the research work of pedagogical methodologists V.A. Dalinger[9].

A differentiated approach to education [3] is the division of students into groups, taking into account their individual characteristics. The main criterion for dividing into groups is their personal interest in studying the subject, their personal attitudes or attitudes towards solving problems in this area, and their ability to assess other practical and prospective values of the area.

A.I. Uman[10], when he calls the information technology approach to education, understands it in a narrow sense - the design of the educational process based on the ordered goals of education; in a broad sense - understands the special organization of the educational process, in which the most important are the procedures for setting specific goals and achieving them [10].

The technological approach to education is implemented through basic technological actions. Among modern pedagogical technologies, information technologies are important. Their application in the pedagogical educational process creates opportunities for the formation of professional skills.

In our republic, in recent years, the development of didactic competence of future primary school teachers, in particular, listeners of retraining courses for pedagogical personnel, the organization of the educational process in primary schools using information technology tools, the development of competent specialists and didactic competence, and the creation of legal and regulatory frameworks for the training of competitive personnel are being created. "Further improvement of the system of continuous education, increasing the capabilities of quality educational services, and continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market" were identified as an important priority task. As a result, the pedagogical possibilities for improving the didactic and methodological activities of future primary school teachers based on pedagogical technologies are expanding.

Based on these analyses in the scientific research work, the process of developing didactic competence of trainees in the process of professional retraining is improved based on the principles of innovative educational technologies, based on the expression of thinking and practical activity, understanding the essence of the phenomenon being studied, and the gradual formation of value-oriented personal thoughts through a verbal-active approach.

Innovative technologies in education are used on the basis of the use of specific approaches to teaching, that is, principles that include the requirements and goals that are the basis for the development of new technologies. All innovations in the pedagogical sphere are based on the fact that they clearly correspond to the current stage of socio-economic development of society. Innovative technologies in education are constantly developing, and their types are expanding. The following main groups of technologies can be distinguished [1]:

1. Information and communication technologies or ICT in the field of science education. The use of these technologies is associated with the development of the information society and the active introduction of information media in all spheres of life. Such technologies are aimed at informatizing the minds of students. Educational programs include new subjects aimed at studying informatics, information processes and ICT. To help increase the information culture of professors, teachers and students, the educational process is also actively informatized;

2. Person-oriented technologies. These technologies are aimed at giving the individual a priority in education and upbringing. The entire educational process is aimed at developing the individual, taking into account the individual's individuality and developmental characteristics.

3. Information and analytical support of the educational process. The use of technologies of this group is aimed at studying the development of each student, class, parallel, educational institution, and their adequate assessment;

4. Monitoring intellectual development. Technologies are based on the use of graphs, a testing system, new assessment methods that allow you to track the dynamics of the development of individual students and the quality of education in general;

5. Educational technologies. The educational process cannot be separated from education. Therefore, new methods of developing the personality and its main qualities are being introduced;

6. Didactic technologies. They are the main factor in the development of an educational institution. Such technologies are based on a set of techniques and tools that include the use of traditional and innovative technologies: independent work with educational literature, the use of audiovisual, multimedia tools, differentiated teaching methods.

Innovative technologies allow you to organize education, direct it in the right direction. There is a large number of general and partial innovative projects in terms of the degree of development of ideas presented in pedagogical science, as well as the possibilities of their use in pedagogical practice. The system of pedagogical practice consists of the following[6]:

1. The system of pedagogical science and pedagogical practice is not new, but constantly relevant and embodies general ideas and practical technologies for the organization of the educational process.

2. The set of all theoretical rules and practical technologies of humanistic pedagogy.

3 It is based on a new ideological approach to the organization and management of pedagogical processes.

4. Technologies based on the use of new ideas and means of informatization and mass communication are considered innovative technologies.

Therefore, in the process of professional retraining, in order to improve the process of developing the didactic competence of trainees based on the principles of innovative educational technologies, expressing thinking and practical activity, understanding the essence of the phenomenon being studied, and gradually forming value-oriented personal thoughts through a verbal-active approach, it is necessary to first study innovative educational technologies, their theoretical and practical aspects.

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